

Synthesis and ecotoxicity screening of reusable, magnetically harvestable metal oxide/hydroxide nanocomposites for safe and sustainable removal and recovery of phosphorus from wastewater

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the ecotoxicological hazard and suggests measures to improve the ecosafety of 10 highly-efficient metal oxide/hydroxide nanocomposite adsorbents for phosphorus removal/recovery from wastewater using the marine bacterium *Vibrio fischeri* - an ecotoxicological test organism commonly used for the screening of chemicals which is especially sensitive to zinc. Nanocomposites were synthesized through simple coprecipitation of two-, three- and four-valent metal precursors (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Zr^{4+}) at different molar ratios, and characterized with laser diffraction, ICP-OES, XRD and SEM. Among these, the pilot-scale tested ZnFeZr-6:1:1-oxyhydroxide was modified by reducing the zinc-fraction to minimize the leaching of harmful Zn^{2+} . The presence of Zn, however, makes the materials technologically powerful by improving the adsorbent selectivity towards phosphate and the material reusability. Composites stability ($d_{50} < 10 \mu\text{m}$) was investigated in deionized water and 2% NaCl (*V. fischeri* test medium) addressing agglomeration, settling and solubilization (releasing metal ions and/or potentially hazardous nanoparticles). All composites, their filtered supernatants and precursor metal salt solutions were evaluated for their toxic potency (half-effective concentration, EC_{50} and minimum bactericidal concentration, MBC) using 30-min kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test (ISO-21338:2010) and 24-h viability assay with bacteria *V. fischeri*. Only the Zn-containing composites showed inhibitory effects to *Vibrio fischeri*. Those with highest zinc-fraction (ZnFeZr-18:5:1; ZnFeZr-10:1:1) were classified "harmful" ($\text{EC}_{50} < 100 \text{ mg/L}$), thus environmentally unsafe for engineering applications. The ZnFeZr-6:1:1 ($\text{EC}_{50} = 118 \text{ mg/L}$, MBC = 250 mg/L) proved assumingly safe once deposited on magnetic particles ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs ($\text{EC}_{50} = 1123 \text{ mg/L}$, MBC > 1000 mg/L). All other composites without Zn were non-toxic to *Vibrio fischeri*.

1. Introduction

Recently, significant efforts were focused on developing materials and technologies for phosphorus recovery from wastewater. Phosphorus (P) is a key nutrient of crucial importance for agriculture and global food security whose natural cycle is severely disrupted by the anthropogenic activity (Withers et al., 2020). Phosphate rock is an intensively exploited finite resource with deteriorating quality, which the EU Commission declared a critical resource already in 2014 due to Europe's strong

import dependency (EU Commission, 2014). Nevertheless, P is also a pollutant commonly removed from wastewater to prevent noxious algal blooms and eutrophication in the receiving waters which may cause severe environmental damage and economic losses (Dodds et al., 2009). Thus, wastewater treatment plants are a major P-sink and untapped secondary source for recovery of the valuable nutrient.

Engineered nanostructured materials, predominantly metal oxides/hydroxides, are frequently reported as excellent adsorbents for phosphate in wastewater (Ooi et al., 2017), although their environmental

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friendliness is not explicitly addressed. Generally, individual nanosized and bulk metal oxides/hydroxides have been well-studied over the years in terms of their toxicity to aquatic organisms, raising special concern for ZnO particles which proved to be highly toxic at both nano- and micro-scale (Aruoja et al., 2015; Bondarenko et al., 2013; Heinlaan et al., 2008). However, combining various 2-, 3- and 4-valent metals co-precipitated as oxides/hydroxides in one nanocomposite material was demonstrated to be much more efficient and selective towards phosphate adsorption, and to improve the long-term adsorbents reusability which is essential for their engineering application (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016). Nevertheless, the uncertainty regarding possible combined adverse effects and ecotoxicological hazards arising from the use of these custom materials has produced new research gaps addressed in this study. The proposed work will upgrade the existing knowledge on ecotoxicity of individual “single-component” nanomaterials by analyzing the synergistic effect between all components of the engineered composites which may act separately or together in terms of ecotoxicity.

Moreover, this work builds on previous research which established the fundamentals of a robust and highly-competitive technology for simultaneous removal and recovery of phosphorus from wastewater (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2017). The technology uses composite micro-sorbents which consist of patented magnetic carrier particles (Mandel et al., 2013) modified with a custom non-magnetic P-selective nanocomposite material, enabling reversible sorption and recovery of phosphorus from aqueous media. The main purpose of this research is to assess the environmental risk and potential toxicity of a custom nanostructured ZnFeZr-oxyhydroxide, previously developed as a highly-efficient phosphate adsorbent (Schneider et al., 2017), immobilized as coating on the magnetic particles to facilitate its easier harvesting.

However, the technological readiness level of the proposed concept still depends on further improvements. In our earlier work, a pilot-scale test was performed to verify the proof-of-concept, upscale the technology and validate its cost-efficient technical implementation (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2017). We could demonstrate also that the material synthesis is easily scalable by successfully producing several kilograms of the magnetic adsorbent. Despite the overall high P-recovery efficiency (> 90%), the upscaling revealed problems with the adsorbent particles' stability by detecting some of their leached precursor metals in the treated effluent, particularly zinc (Zn), as shown in Supplementary Fig. S1. The potential hazard of discharging heavy metals into the aquatic environment must be carefully addressed because zinc is highly toxic to aquatic ecosystems, especially towards algae, already at $\mu\text{g/L}$ -level (Bondarenko et al., 2013).

In this follow-up work, measures are undertaken to optimize the particles' structure by reducing the amount of incorporated Zn^{2+} , assuming this would minimize the leaching of zinc into the treated effluent and receiving water body. The presence of zinc, however, is necessary because it enhances the adsorption selectivity towards phosphate (Schneider et al., 2017). Thus, five variations of the ZnFeZr-material were synthesized using different molar ratios of the precursor metals. Furthermore, five additional metal hydroxide precipitates (CaFe; CaFeZr; CaZnFeZr; MgFeZr and MgZnFe) were synthesized as alternative adsorbent coatings based on previously published multi-criteria screening (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016). Hence, a total of 10 custom nanocomposite P-sorbents were prepared in this study to analyze their potential toxicity using a modified ‘Flash Assay’ protocol (ISO-21338:2010) for acute bioluminescence inhibition of naturally luminescent bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*. This acute toxicity bioassay was chosen specifically because it is a rapid, simple, cost-effective and sensitive method suitable for high-throughput screening of a wide spectrum of chemical substances, including nanomaterials and colored/turbid samples like ours, which is sufficient to make safe-and-sustainable-by-design decisions at the early stages of innovation.

Furthermore, this work investigates the materials' stability under different physicochemical conditions, including solubility of Zn^{2+} ions or leaching of potentially hazardous nanoparticles. Particles size, concentration and solubility have crucial influence on their bioavailability and toxicity (Kahru and Dubourguier, 2010). Thus, special focus was put on the physicochemical properties of the adsorbent particles (concentration, size, chemical composition) which can be modified to exclude any ecotoxic effects from their possible release or leaching of precursor components in the aquatic environment. For further development and scale-up of these highly promising materials and associated technology, it is essential to comply with the “Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design” principle (Caldeira et al., 2022).

Last but not least, the EU Commission published a proposal in October 2022 (EU Commission, 2022) for revising the existing Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD 91/271), driven by the paradigm shift towards circular economy, sustainability and enhanced environmental protection. Among other objectives, this proposal recognizes the acute necessity for nutrients recovery from wastewater, and suggests more stringent discharge limit values for phosphorus, i.e. stricter P-removal requirements. Both these priority objectives can be targeted simultaneously with the proposed technology for P-removal and recovery from wastewater using engineered nanocomposite materials. Therefore, the ultimate goal of this research is to advance the commercialization and full-scale implementation of the technology by verifying its environmentally friendly application.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Synthesis and characterization of various metal oxide/hydroxide nanocomposites as phosphate adsorbents

The synthesis of the metal oxide/hydroxide nanocomposites followed previously published procedure involving simple co-precipitation of pre-dissolved precursor metal salts at $\text{pH} > 10$ (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016; Mandel et al., 2013; Schneider et al., 2017). Detailed description of the synthesis process, including chemical precursors and analytical instrumentation, can be found in Supplementary Material S1.

The choice of metal precursors was based on preliminary screening results (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016), where only certain metal oxide/hydroxides were identified as promising phosphate adsorbents and only the best-performing one, $\text{Zn}^{2+}:\text{Fe}^{3+}:\text{Zr}^{4+} = 6:1:1$, was selected for a subsequent pilot-scale test (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2017).

In this study, five variations of the ZnFeZr-material were synthesized with nominal molar ratios $\text{Zn}^{2+}:\text{Fe}^{3+}:\text{Zr}^{4+} = 18:5:1$; 10:1:1; 6:1:1 (standard); 4:1:1 and 3.6:0.2:1. Furthermore, five additional hydroxide composites were synthesized by incorporating other 2-valent metals to the structure (Ca^{2+} or Mg^{2+}) to either replace or complement Zn^{2+} , namely $\text{Ca}^{2+}:\text{Fe}^{3+} = 2:1$; $\text{Ca}^{2+}:\text{Fe}^{3+}:\text{Zr}^{4+} = 6:1:1$; $\text{Ca}^{2+}:\text{Zn}^{2+}:\text{Fe}^{3+}:\text{Zr}^{4+} = 3:3:1:1$; $\text{Mg}^{2+}:\text{Fe}^{3+}:\text{Zr}^{4+} = 6:1:1$ and $\text{Mg}^{2+}:\text{Zn}^{2+}:\text{Fe}^{3+} = 1:1:1$. These particular nanocomposites were selected as efficient P-sorbents following conclusions from the earlier multi-criteria screening, where only they met all necessary criteria, i.e. high P-adsorption/desorption capacity, selectivity and stability (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016). Moreover, the magnetized version of the standard adsorbent, denominated as ZnFeZr-6:1:1@magnetic particles (MPs), was also tested for toxicity as the baseline material prototype used in the pilot-scale test (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2017).

The synthesis of $\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4/\text{SiO}_2$ magnetic carrier particles (MPs) followed a published procedure (Mandel et al., 2013) and the deposition of the ZnFeZr-adsorbent on the MPs was performed via co-precipitation, described in Supplementary S2.

2.2. Preparation of the metal oxides/hydroxides and their particle-free supernatants, settling tests and quantification in deionized water and in 2% NaCl

The as-synthesized metal oxide/hydroxide composites were diluted with deionized (DI) water (18.2 MΩ, pH 5.6 ± 0.1, Milli-Q/Millipore, Billerica, USA) to obtain 2 g/L stock suspensions (except for the magnetic composite ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs at 5 g/L), sonicated for 2 min (40 W, probe sonicator, Branson-Ultrasonics-Corporation, Danbury, USA) and vortexed before further dilution and use.

The supernatants of all respective composite dilutions were filtered (0.1 µm cellulose acetate filter Minisart®, Sartorius-Stedim-Biotech

GmbH) and also tested for toxicity to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*. The complete methodology, including all tested concentrations of the original composites, their supernatants and precursor salts, is depicted in Fig. 1.

The composites' hydrodynamic size and surface charge (ζ-potential) were measured in 100 mg/L suspensions in DI water with Malvern Zetasizer Nano-ZS in 1 mL DTS1061-folded-capillary-cell and Zetasizer-software 6.32 (Malvern Instruments, UK), utilizing the principles of dynamic light scattering (DLS) and electrophoretic light scattering (ELS), respectively.

Particle settling and solubility tests were performed with all as-synthesized composites in DI water and in 2% NaCl (*V. fischeri* test medium) at concentrations 1–1000 mg/L. The results are visualized in

Fig. 1. Methodology scheme for preparation of the metal oxide/hydroxide composite dilutions, filtered supernatants and their soluble precursor salts for the *Vibrio fischeri* toxicity testing.

Fig. 5 through photographs taken at settling times 0 min, 30 min, 4 h and 24 h. Solubility of the nanocomposites (1000 mg/L suspensions) was analyzed further only in DI water after 0.1 μm sample filtration. The respective metal concentrations in the filtrates were measured using total reflection X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (TRXF; Picofox-S2, Bruker-Nano GmbH, Germany). For this purpose, 50 μL of each filtrate was mixed with gallium (Ga) internal standard (Fluka) at 1:1-ratio. Then, 5 μL of the mixture was pipetted onto a quartz disk. The metal concentrations were quantified with Spectra-software 7.2.5.0 (Bruker-Nano GmbH).

The soluble precursors metal salts used for adsorbent synthesis (ZnCl_2 , $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were also tested for toxicity. Their stock solutions (2 g-Me/L) in DI water had pH 6.3–6.8, i.e. within the recommended range for the *Vibrio fischeri* assay, except for $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (pH 1.9) and $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (pH 1.8).

2.3. Toxicity tests using naturally bioluminescent bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*

2.3.1. Kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test (modified 'Flash Assay')

The acute kinetic bioluminescence inhibition assay (30-min exposure time) with bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* was performed at room temperature ($\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$, maintained with air-conditioning unit) in 96-well microplates (non-tissue culture treated, Greiner-Bio-One) according to the modified Flash-assay standard ISO protocol (ISO-21338:2010, 2010) described in (Mortimer et al., 2008). Briefly, the lyophilized *Vibrio fischeri* bacteria (Aboatox, Turku, Finland) were reconstituted in a diluent containing 20 g/L NaCl, 2.035 g/L $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.3 g/L KCl. All nanocomposite suspensions, chemicals and their two-fold dilutions were prepared in 2% NaCl. Then, 100 μL test solution in 2% NaCl was pipetted into each well and supplemented with 100 μL bacterial suspension in 2% NaCl in Microplate luminometer Orion-II with automatically-controlled dispenser unit, operated with Simplicity-software 4.2 (Berthold-Detection-Systems, Pforzheim, Germany). Bacterial luminescence was continuously recorded in the first 30 s after dispensing, without sample mixing. After 30-min incubation, the luminescence was recorded again. Each test was performed in minimum 3 replicates and each measurement series included both negative (2% NaCl) and positive ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) controls. The inhibition of bacterial luminescence (INH %) by the respective nanocomposite/chemical was calculated as:

$$\text{INH}\% = 100 - \frac{IT_{30}}{\text{KF} \times IT_0} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{KF} = \frac{IC_{30}}{IC_0} \quad (2)$$

The correction factor KF accounts for the control sample natural loss of luminescence (bacterial suspension in 2% NaCl). IC_0 and IT_0 are the maximum luminescence values in the first 5 s after dispensing test bacteria into the control and test samples, respectively. IC_{30} and IT_{30} are the respective luminescence values of control and test sample after 30 min. The half maximal effective concentration (EC_{50}) represents the nominal concentration of a compound reducing the bacterial bioluminescence by 50%. The 30-min EC_{50} values with their respective 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) were calculated from dose-response curves generated with the log-normal model of the REGTOX-software EV7.1.2 for Microsoft Excel™ (Vindimian, 2001). All calculated results were considered statistically significant when the 95% CI did not overlap or $p < 0.05$.

2.3.2. Viability assay ('Spot Test')

Vibrio fischeri viability assay ('Spot test') was performed following the methodology described by Suppi et al. (2015) with a small modification using 2% NaCl for incubation (isotonic medium for marine bacteria *V. fischeri*) instead of deionized water (commonly used for other bacterial strains). The full 'Spot test' procedure is described in Supplementary S3.

This assay evaluates the ability of toxicant-exposed bacteria to form colonies on a toxicant-free nutrient agar after 2-h and 24-h exposure to the tested nanocomposites (toxicants). The colonies were visually analyzed in the dark when bacteria started to emit light and photographed at 48 h. The MBC-values (minimum bactericidal concentration) of the investigated nanocomposites were determined as the lowest tested nominal concentration which inhibited completely the ability of *Vibrio fischeri* to form visible colonies on toxicant-free agar.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physico-chemical characterization of the as-synthesized metal nanocomposites

The synthesis of the 10 nanocomposites followed our previously published fast and simple co-precipitation procedure for layered double hydroxides (LDH) and related structures without any aging steps, air protection or complicated pH-shifts (Mandel et al., 2013). The choice of the 2-, 3- and 4-valent metal precursors and their nominal molar ratios (see Table S1 in Supplementary) to be co-precipitated as oxides/hydroxides in one nanocomposite material was based on preliminary screening (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016). The empirically-found most efficient adsorbent combination $\text{Zn}^{2+}:\text{Fe}^{3+}:\text{Zr}^{4+} = 6:1:1$, referred to as "standard", was investigated further to understand the role of the different material building blocks by varying the metal molar ratios, especially by increasing or decreasing the Zn-fraction (Schneider et al., 2017). Here, the sample synthesis was replicated with focus on decreasing the amount of the potentially toxic Zn^{2+} or replacing it with other non-hazardous 2-valent metals like Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} . Subsequently, all 10 as-synthesized materials (5 ZnFeZr-based and 5 Ca/Mg-containing) were exposed to ecotoxicity tests to fill out the knowledge gap regarding their safe-by-design nature and eco-friendly application.

To verify the chemical composition and actually precipitated molar ratios of the metal precursors, all as-synthesized composites were analyzed with ICP-OES and results are listed in Table S1 in Supplementary. For all 5 ZnFeZr-samples, the measured molar ratios were in good agreement with the theoretical nominal values. However, for the other 5 Ca/Mg-containing samples, there were large deviations between the theoretical and the actual Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} values, where these two metals were only marginally co-precipitated or not detected at all ($\text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{LOD}$ in CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1). This might be because the precursor metal salts were co-precipitated to oxides/hydroxides in a continuously-stirred alkaline NaOH solution (pH 10) and after 5 min the precipitation reaction was stopped by adding acid (HCl) to neutralize the mixtures to pH 7. Thereby, the re-dissolution of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions was probably caused by the acid treatment, resulting in deviations from the precursors' stoichiometry. This confirms the same conclusion from previous work (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016) that the incorporation of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} into the composite structure is either marginal or not possible with this method.

The primary size analysis via laser diffraction showed that all samples had a median diameter in the lower μm -range: $d_{50} = 1\text{--}10 \mu\text{m}$ (Table S1). Thus, none of the composites could be considered pure nanoparticles (NPs). However, as shown in Fig. 2, certain samples like ZnFeZr-18:5:1, 10:1:1, 6:1:1 and MgZnFe-1:1:1 revealed secondary peaks $\sim 100\text{--}300 \text{ nm}$, i.e. the presence of nanoparticles in their structure, mostly likely ZnO NPs, and were analyzed closer for toxicity to *Vibrio fischeri*.

In our earlier work, we disclosed that the standard multi-component material ZnFeZr-6:1:1 consisted of crystalline zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO NPs), surrounded by amorphous zinc, iron and zirconia (oxy)hydroxides (Schneider et al., 2017). Then, we carefully examined the role of each constituent and found evidence that particularly the Zn-fraction and nanostructure of the material have crucial influence on the collaborative action in P-adsorption performance, indicating synergetic effects

Fig. 2. Particle size distribution analysis (primary size) performed with laser diffraction, showing median diameter $d_{50} = 1\text{--}10\ \mu\text{m}$ for all as-synthesized nanocomposites. Left panel: ZnFeZr-based materials; Right panel: Ca-/Mg-containing materials.

between the different components.

In this study, further investigations of the samples' crystallinity with X-ray diffraction (XRD) and samples' morphology with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) were conducted to reveal the structural composition of all replicated as-synthesized materials and verify the possible presence of nanoparticles in their structure.

The X-ray diffractograms in Fig. 3 confirm the presence of ZnO and/or Zn(OH)₂ particles in all ZnFeZr-based samples (top five diffractograms), as concluded in our previous research (Schneider et al., 2017),

which are expected to have potential toxicity effects on *Vibrio fischeri*. The crystallinity of the sample with the highest Zn-fraction ZnFeZr-18:5:1 (first diffractogram from top) can be attributed predominantly to ZnO particles (indicated with “*”) which is in excellent conformity with the previous research results (Schneider et al., 2017), despite of the slight deviations in the measured metal molar ratios of the same sample. Also, the SEM image of ZnFeZr-18:5:1 (Fig. 4a) shows presence of irregularly-shaped small crystals of ZnO nanoparticles, integrated into an amorphous network of Fe and Zr oxides/hydroxides.

Fig. 3. Samples crystallinity analysis with X-ray diffraction (XRD) of all ZnFeZr-based (top five diffractograms) and three Ca-/Mg-containing (bottom three diffractograms) nanocomposites.

Moreover, the particle size distribution analysis (Fig. 2, left panel, top diagram) reveals a secondary peak at 139 nm, also confirming the presence of ZnO nanoparticles.

Sample ZnFeZr-10:1:1 (Fig. 3, second diffractogram from top) appears as a mix of crystalline ZnO and Zn(OH)₂ which matches well with the conclusion by Schneider et al. that less Zn in the structure leads to formation of Zn(OH)₂ instead of ZnO. The SEM image in Fig. 4b also shows evidence for the presence of small ZnO particles and tiny anisotropic structures, possibly Zn(OH)₂, embedded into an amorphous mass of Fe/Zr oxyhydroxides. The secondary peak at 271 nm in size distribution (Fig. 2, left panel, second from top diagram) verifies the presence of sub-micron crystals/ZnO nanoparticles. These two nanocomposites with the highest Zn-fraction (ZnFeZr-18:5:1 and ZnFeZr-10:1:1) are the only ones in which ZnO formation was confirmed by the XRD-results (Fig. 3), and they are expected to show the highest toxicity effect due to the ZnO presence.

For the other ZnFeZr-samples with lower Zn-fraction, the crystalline phase was assigned to Zn(OH)₂ (indicated with “◇”), unlike in the work of Schneider et al., where ZnO particles were detected also in ZnFeZr-6:1:1, and a mix of ZnO and Zn(OH)₂ in ZnFeZr-4:1:1. This could be explained with the different synthesis kinetics in this study, which prevented the formation of ZnO from Zn(OH)₂ condensation, thus leaving more Zn available for Zn(OH)₂ formation. Nevertheless, sample ZnFeZr-3.6:0.2:1 evidently showed only Zn(OH)₂ presence in both cases (this research and (Schneider et al., 2017)) with perfect match in crystallinity, nearly identical molar ratios and chemical composition. The SEM images reveal a web-like structure of solids for ZnFeZr-4:1:1 (Fig. 4d) and ZnFeZr-3.6:0.2:1 (Fig. 4e).

Overall, the XRD results in this work verified consistently the previous conclusions by (Schneider et al., 2017) that the reduction of Zn or

increase of Zr in the ZnFeZr-sample structure leads to the formation of Zn(OH)₂ as the crystalline phase. Exceptionally, only the sample ZnFeZr-6:1:1 showed somewhat a mismatch from Schneider’s XRD results due to the presence of a layered double hydroxide (LDH) structure with reflections for ZnFe_{1.5}(OH)_{4.5}Cl_{0.5} hydrate (marked with “□” in Fig. 3) which differs from the diffractograms showing ZnO particles in Schneider’s case. The LDH-structure is confirmed also by the large hexagonal platelets 1–5 μm in the SEM image (Fig. 4c). Nevertheless, the ICP-OES results in Table S1 in Supplementary verify successful quantitative precipitation of all metal ions in the right molar ratios, meaning that all elements are present in the final as-synthesized solid structure. The mismatch in the XRD-phases, however, could be attributed to the higher Zn- and Fe-fractions incorporated in this material (measured molar ratios: ZnFeZr-6.4:1.2:1.0 in this study vs. 5.3:1.0:1.0 in Schneider’s case) which might have facilitated the LDH-formation. Regardless of the differences, this sample (ZnFeZr-6:1:1) is still highly relevant for the toxicity studies due to the significant Zn-fraction in its chemical composition.

From the other group of Ca-/Mg-containing nanocomposites in the right panel of Figs. 2 and 4, only three of them showed clear crystalline phases in the XRD-analysis: CaFe-2:1; CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1; MgZnFe-1:1:1 (bottom diffractograms in Fig. 3). Generally, the incorporation of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ was either marginal or impossible with this synthesis method, as already discussed earlier and quantified through the ICP-OES measurements in Table S1. Therefore, in sample CaFe-2:1, logically, only hematite (α -Fe₂O₃) crystals were detected as the crystalline phase (marked with “●” in Fig. 3), indicated by the small particulate entities observed in SEM (Fig. 4f). Similar conclusions were made for the same sample CaFe-2:1 in our earlier work, where Ca²⁺ was also not incorporated, and instead of hematite (α -Fe₂O₃), goethite (α -FeO(OH)) was

Fig. 4. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of all as-synthesized nanocomposites. Left panel: ZnFeZr-based materials; Right panel: Ca-/Mg-containing materials.

formed (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016). This is probably due to differently occurring kinetics with a transition between the OH- and O-phases, which are most likely both (hydroxides and oxides) present in the structure, but one is not so prominently expressed in the X-ray diffractograms (e.g. if crystals are still small).

For the nanocomposites CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1 and MgZnFe-1:1:1, as expected, based on earlier findings (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2016), an LDH-structure was formed in both cases, also indicated by the platelets in the corresponding SEM-images (Fig. 4h and j). However, the crystallinity of the two samples is different, showing ZnFe_{1.5}(OH)_{4.5}Cl_{0.5} hydrate (marked with "□") for CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1, and Zn₂Fe(OH)₆Cl hydrate (marked with "■") for MgZnFe-1:1:1. Generally, the synthesis conditions always affect the LDH-crystals quality. Sample MgZnFe-1:1:1

showed all reflections typical for LDH-structures (Mandel et al., 2013) and its respective SEM micrograph (Fig. 4j) revealed LDH-characteristic flaky morphology with agglomerated hexagonally-shaped crystallites (~100–300 nm).

The diffractograms of samples CaFeZr-6:1:1 and MgFeZr-6:1:1 are not included in Fig. 3 due to their prevailing amorphous nature and lack of particulate-like elements in the SEM-images (Fig. 4g and i).

The reader should note that the nanocomposites in this work are very similar, but not perfectly replicating the crystalline structure of the previously synthesized materials (Schneider et al., 2017) due to slight differences in lab conditions, operators and chemical sources, resulting in slightly different precipitation kinetics. This, however, impacts significantly the oxides/hydroxides formation in terms of molar ratios

Fig. 5. Settling of the studied materials' particle suspensions: visualization of their stability in DI water (upper panel) and 2% NaCl (lower panel) at 0 min, 30 min, 4 h and 24 h.

and expression (crystal size) which affects their XRD visibility. Generally, the material analyses revealed mostly similarities, but also deviations, demonstrating that precipitation of solids from pre-dissolved ions requires carefully controlled identical conditions to be exactly reproducible. Nevertheless, the overall „materials' character“ is preserved and despite of the small structural deviations, all conclusions

drawn from the toxicity tests herein should be considered valid for the general case of the studied nanocomposites.

3.2. Stability and characterization of nanocomposite suspensions in deionized (DI) water and in 2% NaCl - particle settling tests and solubility

(Nano)particles tend to agglomerate and settle in aqueous media depending on the media composition. To evaluate this property, particle settling tests were performed in both DI water and in 2% NaCl (test medium for marine bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*). The results in Fig. 5 show rapid sedimentation in 2% NaCl for all samples within the first 30 min, visually detectable especially at the high concentrations >100 mg/L.

The hydrodynamic size (D_h) and ζ -potential were defined only in DI water (100 mg/L suspensions) because measurement in 2% NaCl was impossible due to heavy agglomeration and rapid particle settling, as demonstrated in Fig. 5. The results in Table 1 show that D_h of the various metal oxide/hydroxide particles varied from 186 nm to >1000 nm in DI water. The laser-equipped Malvern-Zetasizer-Nano-ZS device uses the dynamic light scattering (DLS) principle to determine the size distribution of small particles subject to Brownian motion (0.3 nm–10 μ m according to manufacturer's manual). This method, however, is most suitable for particles <1 μ m (Singh et al., 2012) and may show inaccurate results for the larger, fast agglomerating samples such as CaFe-2:1 or MgFeZr-6:1:1. Moreover, according to laser diffraction analysis, all materials have median diameter (primary size) in the lower μ m-range: $d_{50} = 1\text{--}10 \mu\text{m}$ (Table S1) which explains their fast sedimentation, especially in 2% NaCl.

The ζ -potential, reflecting the composites' surface properties and stability, was measured after removing the large particle agglomerates by centrifugation to obtain a reliable value, as recommended by Joonas et al. (2017). For most samples, ζ -potential was positive at neutral pH, varying from +8.3 mV to +27.7 mV (Table 1) which implies low to moderate stability in DI water. Generally, all ZnFeZr-based samples, incl. CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1, were stable in DI water without any visually detectable precipitates even after 24 h settling time (Fig. 5, upper-panel samples). The rest of the samples, Ca- or Mg-containing, had lower ζ -potential (−9.0 mV for CaFeZr-6:1:1 and −12.2 mV for MgFeZr-6:1:1) and higher hydrodynamic particle size (>1 μ m), and logically settled rapidly even in DI water already within the first minutes (Fig. 5, lower-panel samples). Exceptionally, only MgZnFe-1:1:1 with high ζ -potential +27.7 mV and low hydrodynamic size 186 nm, was rather stable in DI water, and remained in suspension for a few hours.

Nevertheless, in 2% NaCl all composites, without exceptions, showed instability due to the shift in surface charge causing electrostatic attraction between the particles and heavy agglomeration effects. Thus, all samples, especially the Ca-/Mg-containing, settled rapidly within the first 30 min, as visualized in Fig. 5. This is expected to affect the toxicity tests (performed in 2% NaCl) through rapid settling of any potentially harmful nanoparticles, preventing contact with the test bacteria. Thus, it is important to carefully analyze other possible sources of toxicity, such

Table 1

Hydrodynamic size (D_h), ζ -potential and pH of the metal oxide/hydroxide nanocomposites measured in 100 mg/L suspensions in deionized (DI) water, and pH in 1000 mg/L suspensions in 2% NaCl. Values are average of 3 measurements ($n = 3$).

Composite name	Hydrodynamic Size (D_h , nm)	ζ -potential in DI water (mV)	pH in DI water	pH in 2% NaCl
ZnFeZr-18:5:1	256	+27.2	6.7	6.6
ZnFeZr-10:1:1	716	+13.7	6.5	6.4
ZnFeZr-6:1:1 (standard)	>1000	+9.2	6.7	6.8
ZnFeZr-4:1:1	376	+14.6	6.9	6.8
ZnFeZr-3.6:0.2:1	658	+8.3	6.6	6.5
CaFe-2:1	>1000	+9.2	8.0	8.1
CaFeZr-6:1:1	>1000	−9.0	7.9	7.8
CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1	>1000	+9.5	6.5	6.6
MgFeZr-6:1:1	>1000	−12.2	8.1	8.2
MgZnFe-1:1:1	186	+27.7	7.2	7.3

as soluble Zn^{2+} ions shed from the particles.

The pH values of all particle suspensions were in the neutral range (pH 6.4–8.2) and compliant with the *Vibrio fischeri* test requirements: pH 6.0–8.5 (ISO-21338:2010, 2010).

Dissolution of metal ions from the studied materials, especially Zn^{2+} , is expected to be one of the main mechanisms of action causing toxicity since Zn was proven toxic to *V. fischeri* already at ~1 mg/L level (Heinlaan et al., 2008). Indeed, the most leached metal from the nano-composite structure in DI water was Zn^{2+} (see Table 2) with concentrations as high as 25.7 mg/L for CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1 (corresponds to 25.7 mg-Zn/g-composite as dry mass), 20.5 mg/L (20.5 mg/g) for the “standard” ZnFeZr-6:1:1 and 10.9 mg/L (10.9 mg/g) for ZnFeZr-4:1:1. Therefore, the filtered supernatants (S) of these 3 samples were expected to show toxicity in the order (S)–CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1 > (S)–ZnFeZr-6:1:1 > (S)–ZnFeZr-4:1:1, which was confirmed by the results in Fig. 6b and Table 3 with EC_{50} -values 490 mg/L, 799 mg/L and 1002 mg/L, respectively, although these concentrations were classified as “not harmful” (>100 mg/L) to *V. fischeri*.

The least amount of Zn^{2+} (0.075 mg/L) in DI water was leached from MgZnFe-1:1:1, and logically, its supernatant had the flattest dose-response curve (Fig. 6b) and proved non-toxic to *V. fischeri*. Generally, all filtered supernatants of the Zn-containing materials were not toxic to *V. fischeri* with $\text{EC}_{50} > 100 \text{ mg/L}$ (see Section 3.3).

The solubility of iron was negligible ($\text{Fe}^{3+} \leq 0.1 \text{ mg/g}$) and zirconium was not detected ($\text{Zr}^{4+} < \text{LOD}$) in any of the samples (Table 2). Calcium and magnesium, however, were still leaching from the composites, even though they were incorporated in very low amounts.

3.3. Toxicity of the studied composites to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*

The toxic potency of the studied composites was evaluated with modified ‘Flash Assay’ and ‘Spot Test’ using the naturally bioluminescent Gram-negative marine bacterium *Vibrio fischeri*, also known as *Aliivibrio fischeri* and *Photobacterium phosphoreum* NRRL-B-11177. It is a commonly-used organism in ecotoxicity testing due to its quick response within seconds to various toxicants which inhibit the bacterial light emission via disruption of the cellular membrane integrity and the bacterial metabolic activity (Kurvet et al., 2017). The decrease in luminescence (light output) is dose-dependent and proportional to the toxicity of the tested chemical.

The *V. fischeri* 30-min kinetic bioluminescence inhibition test (‘Flash Assay’, standard protocol ISO-21338:2010), is a rapid method for initial screening of the acute (eco)toxicity effects of different chemicals. This test has the major advantage to overcome the problems arising from intense color and turbidity in the test samples, like the particle suspensions synthesized in this study. Each sample serves as its own

Table 2

Solubility of the nanocomposites - metal concentrations measured with TXRF in 0.1 μ m-filtered supernatants of 1 g/L particle suspensions in deionized (DI) water. Remark: Values are average of min two measurements with max 5% deviation. The Zr^{4+} values were below the limit of detection (<LOD) for all samples. n.a.: “not applicable”.

Composite name (1 g/L suspensions)	Shedding of solubilized metal ions (mg/L = mg/g-composite dry mass)				
	Zn^{2+}	Fe^{3+}	Zr^{4+}	Ca^{2+}	Mg^{2+}
ZnFeZr-18:5:1	6.9	0.032	<LOD	n.a.	n.a.
ZnFeZr-10:1:1	4.6	0.015	<LOD	n.a.	n.a.
ZnFeZr-6:1:1 (standard)	20.5	0.028	<LOD	n.a.	n.a.
ZnFeZr-4:1:1	10.9	0.035	<LOD	n.a.	n.a.
ZnFeZr-3.6:0.2:1	5.4	0.012	<LOD	n.a.	n.a.
CaFe-2:1	n.a.	0.083	n.a.	9.89	n.a.
CaFeZr-6:1:1	n.a.	0.030	<LOD	5.99	n.a.
CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1	25.7	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	n.a.
MgFeZr-6:1:1	n.a.	0.013	<LOD	n.a.	<LOD
MgZnFe-1:1:1	0.075	0.041	n.a.	n.a.	15.33
ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs	1.095	0.105	<LOD	n.a.	n.a.

Fig. 6. Dose-response curves of all tested samples towards bacteria *Vibrio fischeri*: a) as-synthesized composites, b) precursor salts and 0.1 μm -filtered supernatants of the composites and c) only the “standard” composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1, its magnetic version ZnFeZr 6:1:1@MPs and their respective precursor salts and supernatants. The 30-min EC_{50} values are presented in Table 3. All concentrations are nominal and refer to “mg-compound/L” for all composites and their supernatants before filtration, and “mg-Me/L” for all metal salts. Right panel: a'), b') and c') are the Zn-normalized plots of dose-response curves in a), b), c).

Table 3

Toxicity results to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* of all as-synthesized metal oxide/hydroxide composites, their 0.1 μm -filtered supernatants and soluble precursor metal salts. The listed 30-min EC_{50} values are average ($n = 3$) with the respective 95% confidence intervals included in parenthesis. The 24-h MBC values are representative for three repetitive tests ($n = 3$) with two parallels each. All concentrations are nominal: “composite-based” for the composites, incl. supernatants before filtration (mg-compound/L), and “metal-based” for the metal salts, incl. positive control (mg-Me/L).

Remark: EC_{50} : half-effective concentration; MBC: minimum bactericidal concentration. Hazard ranking based on ecotoxicity classification as described in (Bondarenko et al., 2016).

	Name	30-min EC_{50} (mg/L)	Zn-normalized		
			30-min EC_{50} (mg/L)	24-h MBC (mg/L)	
Composites	ZnFeZr-18:5:1	36.9 (29.0-49.0)	13.5 (10.6-17.9)	100	
	ZnFeZr-10:1:1	53.9 (41.0-70.0)	20.0 (15.2-25.9)	250	
	ZnFeZr-6:1:1	118.0 (93.8-127.0)	30.9 (24.5-33.2)	250	
	ZnFeZr-4:1:1	118.8 (104.8-131.0)	28.7 (25.3-31.6)	100	
	ZnFeZr-3.6:0.2:1	168.2 (141.0-177.0)	42.7 (35.8-44.9)	250	
	CaFe-2:1	non-toxic	non-toxic	>1000	
	CaFeZr-6:1:1	non-toxic	non-toxic	>1000	
	CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1	112.5 (90.9-117.8)	20.6 (16.6-21.5)	250	
	MgFeZr-6:1:1	non-toxic	non-toxic	>1000	
	MgZnFe-1:1:1	486 (391-598)	81.4 (65.5-100)	>1000	
Supernatants (0.1 μm -filtered)	ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs	1123 (929-1173)	58.8 (48.6-61.4)	>1000	
	(S)-ZnFeZr-18:5:1	1643 (1407-1713)	601 (514-626)	>2500	
	(S)-ZnFeZr-10:1:1	2011 (1713-2149)	744 (634-795)	>2500	
	(S)-ZnFeZr-6:1:1	799 (666-778)	209 (174-204)	>2500	
	(S)-ZnFeZr-4:1:1	1002 (853-983)	242 (206-237)	>2500	
	(S)-ZnFeZr-3.6:0.2:1	1395 (1218-1391)	354 (309-353)	>2500	
	(S)-CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1	490 (424-492)	90 (78-90)	>2500	
	(S)-ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs	13637 (8496-31865)	457 (285-1067)	>5000	
Precursor metal salts (stocks 2 g-Me/L)	ZnCl ₂	pH 6.4	17.47 (14.44-17.99)	n.a.	50
	FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	pH 1.9*	1.22 (1.12-1.25)*	n.a.	5*
	ZrOCl ₂ ·8H ₂ O	pH 1.8*	2.20 (2.12-2.22)*	n.a.	10*
	CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	pH 6.3	non-toxic	n.a.	>1000
	MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	pH 6.8	non-toxic	n.a.	>1000
Positive control (stock 5 g-Zn/L)	ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	(as Zn ²⁺)	7.78 (7.13-7.80)	n.a.	50
		Very toxic $\text{EC}_{50} \leq 1$ mg/L	Toxic $1 < \text{EC}_{50} \leq 10$ mg/L	Harmful $10 < \text{EC}_{50} \leq 100$ mg/L	Not classified / not harmful $\text{EC}_{50} > 100$ mg/L

*N.B.: The precursor salts FeCl₃·6H₂O and ZrOCl₂·8H₂O had in test pH 3–5.5, outside the recommended testing range for *V. fischeri* (pH 6–8.5). Adjusting pH with NaOH, however, formed insoluble precipitates which discredits the toxicity results for these two salts.

reference, accounting for color and turbidity correction, thus enabling toxicity evaluation of insoluble and colorful samples. To connect the toxicity data obtained using 30-min bioluminescence inhibition with the bacteria viability after prolonged incubation with the composites (up to 24 h), a viability assay (“Spot Test”) was also conducted. The results from both test formats are presented in Figs. 6 and 7. The hazard ranking of the composites was performed based on EC_{50} -values (Table 3) calculated from dose-response curves (Fig. 6), as described in (Bondarenko et al., 2016): $\text{EC}_{50} \leq 1$ mg/L = very toxic; $1 < \text{EC}_{50} \leq 10$ mg/L = toxic; $10 < \text{EC}_{50} \leq 100$ mg/L = harmful; $\text{EC}_{50} > 100$ mg/L = “not classified/not harmful”. The 30-min EC_{50} values were obtained for 8 out of 11 composites, ranging from 37 mg/L for ZnFeZr-18:5:1 to 1123 mg/L for ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs (see Table 3).

The composites with highest Zn-fraction: ZnFeZr-18:5:1 and ZnFeZr-

10:1:1 (30-min $\text{EC}_{50} = 36.9$ mg/L and 53.9 mg/L, respectively) were ranked as “harmful” (Fig. 6a), which complies with the XRD-results confirming the presence of harmful ZnO nanoparticles in their structure (Fig. 3). The lethal endpoint from ‘Spot test’, however, was reached after 24-h incubation, resulting in MBC-values 100 mg/L and 250 mg/L, respectively (Fig. 7a). In fact, all Zn-containing composites had 24-h MBC = 250 mg/L or even 100 mg/L (for ZnFeZr-18:5:1 and 4:1:1), except for MgZnFe-1:1:1 with 24-h MBC >1000 mg/L. This correlates well with the 30-min EC_{50} -values in Table 3 where all Zn-containing compounds fell either in the “harmful” range ($10 < \text{EC}_{50} \leq 100$ mg/L) or close to it with $\text{EC}_{50} \sim 100$ mg/L. Only MgZnFe-1:1:1 was considered “not harmful” ($\text{EC}_{50} = 486$ mg/L), most likely due to the limited solubility of Zn²⁺: only 0.075 mg/g (Table 2).

The luminescence inhibition (EC_{50} -data) of *V. fischeri* caused by

Fig. 7. Viability of *Vibrio fischeri* and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) after 2-h and 24-h exposure to: **a)** the 10 as-synthesized composites and **b)** the standard composite ZnFeZr 6:1:1, its magnetic version ZnFeZr 6:1:1@MPs and their respective filtered particle-free supernatants. Remark: Viability was determined based on the colony-forming ability of the bacteria exposed to the tested compounds in 2% NaCl for 2 h and 24 h at room temperature (~20 °C). After exposure, 3 μ L bacterial suspension was transferred to a toxicant-free agarized nutrient medium and plates were incubated for 48 h at room temperature. Blue-green spots are bioluminescent bacterial colonies from the 2-h and 24-h toxicants exposure photographed in the dark after 48-h incubation. MBC is the lowest tested concentration which inhibited completely the bacterial growth (no visible colonies detected); 24-h MBC-values are listed in Table 3. All concentrations are nominal and refer to “mg-compound/L”, incl. supernatants before filtration (except for positive control: “mg-Zn/L”). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

toxicants is a sub-lethal response which does not fully reflect the cell viability, but it correlated with the viability/mortality endpoint (MBC-data), i.e. the 24-h MBC values were ~2-fold higher than the 30-min EC₅₀-values (Table 3), explained with the different sensitivity of endpoints, namely inhibition of bioluminescence *versus* inhibition of growth (Heinlaan et al., 2008).

All other Zn-free composites, irrespective of their composition, showed no acute inhibitory effect on the bioluminescence even at the highest tested concentration: 24-h MBC >1000 mg/L (Fig. 7a) and were thus non-toxic, i.e. without any acute toxicity effects to *Vibrio fischeri* (Table 3). This confirms the assumption that the acute toxicity effects of the nanocomposites were attributed only to the presence of Zn²⁺ and ZnO, and that the leaching of Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ did not cause any inhibition of bioluminescence. The decrease in bacterial bioluminescence upon exposure to the Zn-containing composites was assumingly due to interactions with the bacterial outer membrane. All Zn-based composites were positively charged at neutral pH (see ζ -potential in Table 1) predisposing for their strong electrostatic attraction and attachment to

the negatively charged *Vibrio fischeri* cell membrane (ζ -potential -21.8 mV according to (Kurvet et al., 2017)). The sensitivity of *Vibrio fischeri* to bioavailable Zn²⁺ ions and ZnO was researched by others and reported toxicity values for ZnO (both bulk and nano-sized) were in the range 30-min EC₅₀ = 1.8–11.5 mg/L (Aruoja et al., 2015; Heinlaan et al., 2008; Mortimer et al., 2008), confirming that zinc compounds are intrinsically biocidal and quite toxic to *Vibrio fischeri*. In contrast, the Zn-free composites CaFeZr-6:1:1 and MgFeZr-6:1:1 had negative ζ -potentials (Table 1) and were probably repelled by the negatively charged bacterial cells, thus preventing interactions with the bacteria. This explains also the lack of acute toxicity of the latter two composites to *V. fischeri*.

The hazard ranking of the composites based on average 30-min EC₅₀ values (Table 3) follows the order: ZnFeZr-18:5:1 > ZnFeZr-10:1:1 > CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1 ~ ZnFeZr-6:1:1 ~ ZnFeZr-4:1:1 > ZnFeZr-3.6:0.2:1 > MgZnFe-1:1:1 > ZnFeZr-6:1:1@MPs, showing a logical increase in acute toxicity potential with an increasing Zn-content. This order, however, is not compliant with the order of solubilized/shed Zn²⁺ ions in DI water (Table 2), according to which the composites leaching the most zinc

should be most toxic, i.e. $\text{CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1} > \text{ZnFeZr-6:1:1} > \text{ZnFeZr-4:1:1} > \text{ZnFeZr-18:5:1} \sim \text{ZnFeZr-10:1:1} \sim \text{ZnFeZr-3.6:0.2:1}$. Possible reason for this discrepancy is that Zn-leaching was analyzed in DI water, not taking into account the impact of the 2% NaCl medium, which obviously had strong agglomeration effect (see Fig. 5) by changing the particle surface charge and causing fast sedimentation of the composites with higher hydrodynamic size, e.g. CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1 , thus reducing their toxicity in 2% NaCl. Moreover, it has been demonstrated that Zn^{2+} ions are not 100% bioavailable in 2% NaCl and are therefore less toxic in the *V. fischeri* test environment (Heinlaan et al., 2008).

The precursor metal salts were also tested for toxicity due to their solubility and shedding of directly bioavailable metal ions. As expected, ZnCl_2 was in the “harmful” range with 30-min $\text{EC}_{50} = 17.5 \text{ mg-Zn}^{2+}/\text{L}$, which is comparable with the toxicity of the positive control $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$: 30-min $\text{EC}_{50} = 7.8 \text{ mg-Zn}^{2+}/\text{L}$ (Table 3). Expectedly, $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were not toxic to *V. fischeri*. The precursor salts $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{ZrOCl}_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ had in test pH 3–5.5, outside the recommended testing range for *V. fischeri* (pH 6–8.5). Adjusting pH with NaOH, however, formed insoluble precipitates which discredits the toxicity results for the latter two salts.

The so-called “standard” material ZnFeZr-6:1:1 was borderline “harmful” (Fig. 6c, green curve) with 30-min $\text{EC}_{50} = 93.8\text{--}127 \text{ mg/L}$ (Table 3) and 24-h MBC = 250 mg/L, with strong inhibitory effect already at 100 mg/L (Fig. 7b, first row). Taking into account the actually precipitated molar ratio ZnFeZr-6.4:1.2:1 (see Table S1 in Supplementary) and normalizing by elemental Zn (~26 wt%), this value dropped to 30-min $\text{EC}_{50} = 24\text{--}33 \text{ mg-Zn/L}$, which is indisputably in the “harmful” range. Furthermore, the Zn-normalized EC_{50} -values in Table 3 show that all Zn-containing composites become “harmful”, including those with reduced Zn amount (ZnFeZr-4:1:1 and $3.6:0.2:1$), once their 30-min EC_{50} -values are normalized by elemental Zn (Zn-fractions in wt% are listed in Table S1). This effect is visualized also by shifting all dose-response curves to the left after Zn-normalization (compare Fig. 6a', b', c' vs. Fig. 6a, b, c).

Realistic adsorbent/composite concentrations for engineering applications are in the range 200–1000 mg/L depending on the phosphate concentration in wastewater (Drenkova-Tuhtan et al., 2017). According to the *Vibrio fischeri* acute toxicity results, such concentrations would have ecotoxic effects, especially if Zn-normalized. Therefore, it is not recommended to apply the Zn-containing adsorbents directly in the biological treatment step of a wastewater treatment plant which may have inhibitory effects on the activated sludge biomass. Ideally, P-adsorption should take place as a separate step after biological pre-treatment of the wastewater.

The filtered supernatant of the “standard” material started to show some luminescence inhibition ~2000 mg/L (particle concentration before filtration) (Fig. 7b, second row). Nevertheless, once deposited onto magnetic particles, the same material $\text{ZnFeZr-6:1:1}@\text{MPs}$ was rather stable and did not show any inhibition of bioluminescence even at the highest concentration: 24-h MBC >1000 mg/L (Fig. 7b, third row) and 30-min $\text{EC}_{50} > 1000 \text{ mg/L}$ (Table 3, Fig. 6c, orange curve).

All filtered supernatants had 24-h MBC >2500 mg/L and their dose-response curves were in the far right of the toxicity spectrum (Fig. 6b, grey curves) yielding high 30-min $\text{EC}_{50} > 490 \text{ mg/L}$, meaning that they are practically non-toxic to *Vibrio fischeri* in the tested concentration range 1–2500 mg/L (corresponds to particle concentration before filtration). Exception was the supernatant (S)- CaZnFeZr-3:3:1:1 classified as “harmful” after Zn-normalization of EC_{50} , which coincides with the results in Table 2 showing that this material leached the most Zn^{2+} .

From an engineering perspective, this means that even at the highest concentration and despite the leaching of Zn^{2+} , the application of all adsorbents should be safe for the aquatic environment, as long as the adsorbent harvesting and separation process is well-secured within the controlled engineering facility environment. However, more inclusive ecotoxicity tests, including investigation of chronic effects, must be performed also with other model organisms from different trophic levels

in the aquatic food-web. Further tests are currently ongoing with other test organisms such as freshwater crustacean *Daphnia magna* and green algae *Raphidocelis subcapitata* and the outcome of these tests will be reported in a follow-up publication. Furthermore, it should be noted that the physico-chemical properties of the effluent receiving natural water body may increase or decrease the bioavailability of the toxicants, especially important when studying the chronic toxicity effects to freshwater organisms. Parameters such as pH and temperature may increase the solubilization and bioavailability of free toxic Zn-ions, and the presence of humic substances, suspended solids and high salinity may lead to agglomeration and sedimentation of potentially harmful nanoparticles, respectively decrease their bioavailability.

4. Conclusions

This study addressed the knowledge gap regarding the environmental safety of 10 highly-efficient metal oxide/hydroxide nano-composite adsorbents for phosphate, in compliance with the “Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design” principle, important for the further commercialization of the materials.

The adsorbents synthesis was successfully replicated following established procedures. The materials' structure and composition were compared against previously published data and similarities were verified via Laser Diffraction, SEM, XRD and ICP-OES analysis.

Stability tests showed that all Zn-containing materials leached potentially toxic Zn^{2+} ions. Moreover, the composites with highest Zn-fraction (ZnFeZr-18:5:1 , ZnFeZr-10:1:1) revealed presence of hazardous ZnO nanoparticles, and were indisputably “harmful” to bacteria *Vibrio fischeri* (30-min $\text{EC}_{50} < 100 \text{ mg/L}$). Therefore, main focus was laid on reducing the Zn-content in their composition. Nonetheless, all Zn-containing composites, without exception, showed inhibitory effects of acute toxicity to bacteria *V. fischeri* and their Zn-normalized 30-min EC_{50} -values (14–59 mg-Zn/L) were all in the “harmful” range ($10 < \text{EC}_{50} \leq 100 \text{ mg/L}$). The 24-h MBC-values were 100–250 mg-compound/L. The rest of the composites without Zn were non-toxic to *V. fischeri*.

Nevertheless, once deposited onto magnetic particles, the “pilot-scale”-tested material $\text{ZnFeZr-6:1:1}@\text{MPs}$ didn't show any inhibition of bioluminescence ($\text{EC}_{50} > 1000 \text{ mg/L}$; $\text{MBC} > 1000 \text{ mg/L}$) and was considered safe for engineering applications. Despite the leaching of Zn^{2+} , the filtered supernatants of all composites were also non-toxic to *V. fischeri*, meaning that their application should be safe for the aquatic environment, as long as the adsorbent harvesting and separation process is well-secured within the controlled engineering facility.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Asya Drenkova-Tuhtan: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mariliis Sihtmäe:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Kevin Uke:** Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Heiki Vija:** Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Maximilian Oppmann:** Visualization, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Johannes Prieschl:** Visualization, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Karl Mandel:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anne Kahru:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2024.141287>.

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